

The Impact of Teacher Personality Traits on Student Learning: Unveiling an Essential Dimension in Educational Psychology

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ABSTRACT: Within the field of educational psychology, the impact of teacher's personality traits on student learning outcomes has become more widely acknowledged, posing a challenge to the conventional emphasis on curriculum design and pedagogical strategies alone. The present research integrates extant literature and empirical data to investigate the complex correlation between teacher's personality traits & student learning, with a focus on the consequences for instructional design and policy development. Teacher's personality traits have a big impact on student learning and classroom environment. The results highlight how crucial it is to take teacher personality into account when hiring, selecting, and developing new teachers. They also provide guidance for developing encouraging classroom environments that help students achieve their goals. In addition, the incorporation of teacher personality traits into the theoretical framework of educational psychology enhances our comprehension of the reciprocal nature of the teacher-student interaction and effective teaching practices.

Keywords: Teacher personality traits, student learning, educational psychology, Five-Factor Model, teaching effectiveness, student engagement, academic achievement, socio-emotional well-being

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1. Introduction

The design of curricula and pedagogical strategies has historically been the main determinants of student learning outcomes in educational psychology (Alexander & Fox, 2018). Although these factors definitely have a big influence on how schools operate, research in the last few years has focused more and more on how teachers' personalities affect how their students develop (Trapmann et al., 2007). This change in emphasis recognizes that good teaching entails complicated human relationships within the classroom setting, rather than just imparting knowledge (McCrae & Costa, 1987).

Teachers' personalities, which are frequently thought of as constant personal traits (Goldberg, 1993), can have a big impact on students' learning experiences and results (Chamorro, 2003). For example, extraversion may affect a teacher's capacity to involve

students in classroom activities (Oxford, 1995), but conscientiousness may be related to the efficiency and organization of instruction. In the principality of educational psychology, the influence of teacher personality traits has collected relatively less attention, despite their potential significance and importance in educational settings (Brooders et al., 2011).

By examining the influence of teacher's personality traits on student learning outcomes, this study aims to close this knowledge gap and improve our understanding of effective teaching strategies and methodology. We hope to shed light on the complex relationship between teacher's personality traits and student's growth by investigating the sometimes disregarded aspects and features of teacher personality traits.

2. Literature Review

In the field of educational psychology, in many researches it has been seen that there is an impact of teacher's personality traits on student learning outcomes and growth in educational setting is becoming more widely acknowledged. Although curriculum design, classroom environment and teaching strategies have received most of the attention in traditional pedagogical theories, new research has shown how important and crucial it is to take into account teachers' unique qualities and personality's traits in order to understand student's growth in an educational setting. (Barrick et al., 1998).

The Five-Factor Model (FFM), which includes the traits of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience (McCrae & Costa, 1987), is one of the most important and extensively researched personality frameworks in relation to education. A wealth of empirical data substantiates the idea that these personality dimensions have a major impact on student learning outcomes and teaching effectiveness in the classroom (Chamorro, 2003). There is a need to shift from the traditional methods of appointing teachers solely based on qualifications, degrees and political influence. A teacher must possess personality traits as well as the ability to properly teach his students. For the exploration of these constructs, focus group interviews were conducted. The study showed that students can assess the effectiveness of teaching based on their personal experiences and can form an opinion about it. Flaws in the hiring culture and the need to give importance to student feedback and evaluation have been highlighted. Teacher training programs must be conducted by policy makers to equip teachers with the mandatory skills and mindsets. According to this study teachers can positively affect student productivity by the use of problem solving, if their teaching methods are on the same level as the students' intellectual features (Ibad, 2024). To be a successful teacher, one must have the attributes of passion, cooperation, and patience. Students' learning process is directly influenced by the teacher's personality. A research was conducted on the teachers of West Bengal according to the Big Five Inventory introduced by Goldberg (1993).

Teachers were found to be less reserved and more fun loving, extraverted and were more conscientious. They were more creative and hence more open to experience, however they reported being less agreeable. The study conducted that teachers had varying degrees of the big five factors and had balanced personalities. This balance positively affects a teacher's performance. (Karmakar et al., 2024) Greater teacher-student

interaction and engagement have been linked to extraversion, which is characterized by friendliness, assertiveness, and excitement (Chamorro, 2003). Extraverted teachers often create lively, engaging classrooms that encourage student engagement and motivation. On the other hand, introverted educators could find it difficult to promote classroom relationships and might unintentionally reduce student participation (Oxford, 1995). Another important personality attribute associated with effective teaching is conscientiousness, which is characterized by organization, dependability, and goal-directedness. Precise planning and implementation of learning activities by conscientious teachers results in higher academic accomplishment from their pupils (Trapmann et al., 2007). According to Brokers et al. (2011), their methodical approach to education improves classroom management and fosters a structured learning environment that is favorable to student performance. A study was conducted in a high school in Saudi Arabia which investigates the relationship between the teacher's personality traits and students' motivation to learn the English speaking language. It was a self-reported survey.

According to the study there is a positive correlation between teacher's personality traits and students' learning outcome. Teacher is the main factor which helps in influencing the students to build interest and give proper attention in their studies. In current study, teacher's show high scores in positive personality traits, so that their students show high scores in motivation in learning. Teacher's positive traits have a big influence on a student's motivation to learn. Teachers' traits and qualities are a very important tool to build and shape a student's learning outcome (Alrishan et al., 2023). Research concluded that student's self-efficacy is very important for a student and has a positive impact on the student's learning outcome, teacher's personality traits moderate the relationship between student's self-efficacy and their learning outcome. When teachers have positive personality traits, student's performance in learning their subject gets stronger and better. Studies suggest that educators should take notice of a teacher's personality traits while developing new educational programs for students. Teachers who portray a positive attitude towards their students and their teaching skills, their students will engage more in classroom activities and develop confidence in them to take risks. Research also suggests that teacher's with positive personality traits like extraversion and outgoing personality traits help a lot in engaging and participating in classroom activities (Tengaa, 2024).

Teacher's personality traits are a very influential tool to develop interest and motivation in students for performing well in studies. It is very important for teachers to have a good bond with students because when teachers have a positive relationship with students and show warm and supportive behavior towards their students which will create a safe and supportive classroom environment for the student, students will feel comfortable to ask questions and take risks when they need to. Enthusiastic teachers show passion towards their students to teach them new lessons with different teaching methods. Moreover, emotionally intelligent teachers more easily understand and manage their emotions as well as teachers easily recognize, acknowledge and respond to their student's emotional needs. Every student is different so they need different teaching methods to understand their lessons. Teachers with adaptability show different ways of teaching styles according to their understanding of their student's requirements and needs (Iqbal et al., 2024). Teacher's psychological capital moderated with traits is also very helpful in

educational settings. Teachers with high hopes, optimistic behavior and self-efficacy are more driven to do creative teaching and explore new teaching methods which create a more engaging classroom environment and students take part in classroom activities. Conscientiousness personality traits in teachers help in building a more productive environment in the classroom. Teachers with conscientious personality traits are more goal oriented and organized and their only focus is student's achievement. Teacher's personality traits play a very effective role for effective learning in the classroom environment and innovative behavior in teachers (Mousavi & Ebrahimi, 2024). Teacher's personality traits are a very important factor in shaping students behavior. Students of approachable teachers take risks and participate in class activities without any fear and hesitation. Teachers who are willing to sacrifice their needs for their student's achievement and betterment are more helpful for their students (Syahrul et al., 2024).

Teachers contain personality traits that are directly helpful in daily life, are more likely to inspire and manage their workload effectively and become a good self-leader (Abdi et al., 2024). In every university education it is very important to have positive personality traits other than knowledge and teaching skills to create a positive learning environment. Teachers should have qualities and personality traits like Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Openness and Agreeableness to build a creative and positive learning environment. Openness allows teachers to create and promote new teaching methods and convey effectiveness. Teachers with trait agreeableness are more helpful, build supportive environments and are more helpful. Teachers with extraversion traits are open to new ideas and make good connections with students. Moreover teachers with Conscientiousness traits portray more guidance and support towards their students. When a teacher contains all these characteristics of positive personality traits, it builds an inspiring and ideal educator (Afida et al., 2024). A study was conducted to investigate the relationship between teacher's personality traits and their disposition to share knowledge. Study focuses on big five personality traits. All of the personality traits except for conscientiousness has a significant and notable impact on knowledge sharing behavior of teachers (Agyemang et al., 2016). Educators who work with children who are at early childhood developmental stage, evaluate themselves and have high score on all big five personality traits. Early childhood educators who scored high in extraversion, it has been seen that they have good interaction with children and are more responsive towards children (Burns et al., 2024). A study was conducted on principals with the perspectives of the teachers of the school in Jerusalem. It has been seen that overall personality traits were 72.1%. The strongest personality traits among the principals were conscientiousness which is 72.6% and the weakest personality trait among the principals are control which is 70.1%. The strongest soft skill was communication and the weakest was networking. Results shows that there is a positive correlation between personality traits and soft skill which describe as according to the perspective of the teachers, principals who have high score in personality traits have strong personality and have strong soft skills as well (Gul, 2024). A model proposed in a study which predicts that there is a positive relation between a student's academic performance and teacher's personality traits. (Shaninah & Noor, 2024). According to a study, teacher's personality traits also influence job satisfaction in educators. Study was conducted in a public university of Pakistan where an open-ended questionnaire was used to evaluate the job satisfaction in educators. It has seen that people with high scores in personality traits

have job satisfaction and work more properly and are more satisfied with their workplace. It indicates that positive personality traits have a strong positive relationship with job satisfaction (Shah et al., 2024).

Teaching is the cycle that works with learning furthermore, requires an equilibrium of many elements in genuine execution information, ability, and characteristics of character. As A. Bartlett Giamatti brought up, Instructing is an instinctual workmanship, aware of potential, hankering of acknowledgement, a stopping, consistent cycle. In any case, an educator is the individual whose occupation is to give guidelines and to spread the word, particularly at school. The manner by which the instructor introduces himself can impact his partners, guardians, and understudies. Frequently, understudies interface the inclination of a specific dependent upon the instructor and how the subject ought to be instructed. (Shaninah & Noor, 2024). A study was conducted to investigate the relationship between teacher's personality traits and their commitment to school. According to a study, teacher's personality traits as well as ethical views take a crucial part in shaping and developing dedication in teachers for their schools and organizations. Adapting a competitive environment in school and proper commitment with their work has been seen in those educators. Study talks about three traits which are extraversion, conscientiousness and agreeableness which shows positive correlation with the teacher's commitment to their work. These traits are common in those educators who are more ethically committed with their work and school (Sheikh et al., 2024).

In a research, teacher's big five personality traits and their small aspects on student learning have been studied. Student rated their instructors on the basis of how they perceived their instructor during lectures in classroom and their effective teaching strategies. Teacher's personality traits have impact on student's perception. Teacher's personality traits like conscientiousness and agreeableness plays a big role in shaping student's perception which also positively affects students' learning outcome. Teacher's personality traits are a main factor through which a person understands the effectiveness of teaching methods (Buric et al., 2023). Unfortunately there is a lack of knowledge sharing behavior in academic environments. Personality traits deeply influence knowledge sharing behavior. The five personality traits that must be considered are: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. Written contributions, organizational communication, personal interactions, and communities of practice, all are positively predicted by openness to experience. However agreeableness also predicts organizational communication and extraversion predicts communities of practice. These four fields converge to form a knowledge sharing behavior. Different strategies must be adopted to foster knowledge sharing in higher educational institutions (Shaukat et al., 2023). During Covid-19 students and teachers were forced to take online classes. According to a study, self-efficacy and self-innovativeness plays a very crucial part in a teacher's teaching capabilities and also it affects a student's learning outcome. Teachers who have personality trait like self-accountability are more likely to show responsibility towards student's learning outcome. Also the success rate of students in distant learning is better in those teachers who have self-innovativeness and feel more confident in teaching with new tools and techniques because this trait has a great influence on all other factors which have been seen in the study. These teachers use creative

teaching methods which develop interest to study in students. Teachers with this trait also feel confident teaching remotely than those teachers who don't have self-innovativeness. Self-efficacy and self-innovativeness improve and influence teaching effectiveness (Vidergor, 2023).

Research explored the relation between teachers' traits, particularly gratitude, and stipulated that this trait is positively related to work engagement and negatively associated with burnout. It said the teachers who showed gratitude showed fewer symptoms of burnout as compared to the others. This shows that a positive attitude and trait is essential for teachers in their professional work and cultivating the trait in teachers may reduce the degree of burnout in teachers to low. Therefore, fostering an environment in educational settings where gratitude is important could potentially improve teacher well-being as well as job performance (Nicuta et al., 2023). Another study that explores the impact of teachers' personality and academic performance in schools suggests that personality traits like extraversion, introversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and neuroticism greatly influence students' academic outcomes. The results showed that the traits exhibited by the teachers like patience, openness, supportiveness, etc. positively affected the performance of the students however, the degree of influence was variable and Some traits showed more effect than others (ALPHONSINE & Andala, 2022)

There are many factors which help in building a more effective learning environment but teacher's personality traits are one of the most important factors. There is a direct relationship between big five personality traits and students' motivation in learning. This predicts that highly sociable teachers may intentionally increase the students' desire to learn as compared to the disciplined and competent teachers (Khalilzadeh & Khodi, 2021). The study investigated how the five personality traits in teachers' personalities influence learners' Foreign Language Enjoyment (FLE). The results indicated that these traits positively impacted the learners and enhanced their academic performance by fostering a positive atmosphere in the classroom. However, the traits with mildly negative connotations i.e. conscientiousness and neuroticism did not show significant effects. This shows the importance of a teacher's personality in shaping the effective learning environment (Ahmadi-Azad et al., 2020). The article highlights the impact of personality traits of teachers on the teaching practices and the response of the students towards those behaviors. It was seen that extroverted teachers display traits like being lively, sociable, and assertive. It also suggests that students learn from the personality of teachers and adopt certain traits that their teachers have. So we can say that effective teaching is primarily linked to creating an environment that supports the learning of students (Chimezie , 2020).

By using scales big five inventory, it has been seen that meditation is influenced by personality traits in teachers. Also, it makes educators and instructors less neurotic and more responsive. Mindfulness Meditation (MM) is a type of thoughtful practice initially created in the Buddhist practice and presented throughout recent years in the West. Care alludes to a quality of mindfulness that can be depicted as the singular's familiarity with and consideration regarding one's present time and place mental and somatosensory experience (e.g., contemplations, feelings, and substantial sensations). Personality traits help in practicing mindfulness. It has been seen that those who are involved in mindfulness activities have more positive personality traits (Fabbro et al., 2020). Those teachers who

have high scores in personality traits of mindfulness and conscientiousness are involved in mindfulness meditation. Teacher's with personality traits show effective stress management in the workplace. According to another point of view, MM has been utilized as a likely intercession for further developing people's mental prosperity and working environment results, with explicit trial of whether encouraging coping may be valuable abilities for business related pressure and burnout. To be sure, earlier examination has shown that care based medications might help providing care experts (e.g., instructors, medical attendants, doctors) adapt to conceivable burnout side effects (Fabbro et al., 2020).

Teacher's performance highly depends on the teacher's personality traits. (Kell, 2019). As per Canto-Herrera and Salazar-Carballo (2010), the student's scholastic exhibition relies upon the conveyance of guidance. Juvova (2015) states that an instructor needs incredible abilities and positive personality traits and novel capacities which straightforwardly influence a student's accomplishments. Instructors' responsibility is additionally a significant viewpoint to increment school understudies' inspiration and execution (Berry 2016). A research was conducted on 300 teachers to see teacher's personality traits on willingness to share knowledge. It has been seen that personality traits are a big factor and 4 out of 5 personality traits have a big impact on knowledge sharing attitude and behavior among teachers (Agyemang et al., 2016).

The article's focus was primarily based on the personality traits possessed by teachers. The five factor model of personality (FFM) was used in the study which identifies five areas which are extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. Within each domain are six additional facets. Upon assessments, it was found that teachers were more agreeable and extraverted as compared to the general population. Teachers more open to experience were found to be at a greater likelihood to work at schools where children came from challenged and difficult circumstances. According to EVAAS estimates, a teacher is more effective if he/she is more conscientious, but less effective if he/she is more agreeable. It was concluded that schools must consider personality trait measures during the teacher hiring process (Bastian et al., 2015). Mkpanang (2015) states that close to home solidness is a vital component of capability of an educator. Researcher stresses that educators should remain genuinely cognizant to change student's comprehension that prompts the topic of the instructor's character and personality traits. Garcia (2010) shows that accommodating relations with students and instructors frequently increments students' scholarly presentation on the grounds that the affinity among students and educators makes significant indicators persuade the student's in light of their scholarly presentation. Yunus, Osman, and Ishak (2011) portrayed that hopeful instructor understudy relations increment inspirational level and furthermore work on their scholar accomplishment. They accomplish exceptional grades in those subjects when shown by their adored educators. It implies that the nearby relationship with educators helps and persuades students in their learning. As suggested by Blazar and Kraft (2017), instructors upgrade grades and convey a helpful climate that gives students common and expressive development, and school conduct. As a sign of emotional instability and stress vulnerability, neuroticism can have a detrimental effect on student results and the efficacy of instruction. According to Brokers et al. (2011), educators with a high neuroticism level may display emotional instability and struggle to manage the

responsibilities of the classroom, which can cause disruptions in instruction and lower student involvement. In conclusion, research points to a substantial relationship between teacher personality qualities and student learning outcomes, which has consequences for both instructional strategy and educational policy. Enhancing teaching effectiveness and fostering happy learning environments can be aided by an understanding of the relationship between teacher personality and student growth.

There exists a correlation between emotional intelligence and satisfaction with life. Emotional intelligence has a better predictive validity as compared to the traditional measures of intelligence. People who have a higher EI are less likely to engage in activities giving them short term pleasures and are more focused on self-growth. A study conducted to examine the correlation between EI and personality traits in school teachers showed that extraversion was linked with some meaningful purpose in life. It was found that the mental wellbeing of teachers was greatly predicted by neuroticism, conscientiousness, and extraversion. However further research needs to be conducted to get the true understanding of the relationship between EI and psychological well-being among teachers (Avsec et al., 2009). Innovative teaching methods and curriculum design have been linked to openness to experience, which reflects curiosity, inventiveness, and adaptability (Chamorro, 2003). Instructors with high levels of openness often integrate a variety of viewpoints and teaching strategies, encouraging students' critical thinking and intellectual curiosity (Chamorro, 2003). The classroom climate and the quality of the interactions between teachers and students are influenced by agreeableness, which is characterized by warmth, empathy, and cooperation (Chamorro, 2003). In addition to encouraging pleasant social interactions and students' emotional well-being, agreeable teachers create a loving and helpful learning atmosphere (Chamorro, 2003) Additionally, they might be better at adjusting to shifting educational environments and integrating cutting-edge technologies into their instruction (Oxford, 1995).

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3. Significance of Study

This study holds significant implications for educational practice and policy, particularly in the context of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) as a diverse and multicultural society. This study adds to our understanding of successful teaching strategies and how they affect students' growth by examining the impact of teacher personality factors on student learning outcomes. The UAE is a country where people from different countries and cultures live side by side, making the function of teachers as intermediaries of educational

advancement even more important. Due to its multicultural population, which includes expats from all over the world, the United Arab Emirates offers both educational opportunities and problems. Recognizing the impact of teacher personality qualities on student engagement, academic performance, and socio-emotional health can help to create inclusive and culturally sensitive learning environments.

Additionally, the results of this study can help improve teacher professional development initiatives in the United Arab Emirates. Understanding the significance of a teacher's personality in the context of the UAE's multicultural culture can help with the planning of professional development programmes that give teachers the knowledge and abilities they need to interact with students from a variety of cultural backgrounds. Moreover, including teacher personality traits into educational psychology's theoretical framework enhances our comprehension of successful teaching strategies in a range of cultural contexts. Acknowledging the influence of teacher personality on classroom dynamics can help implement more inclusive and culturally responsive educational practices in the United Arab Emirates, a country that celebrates and values cultural variety.

Eligibility Criteria:

Strict eligibility requirements were set in order to guarantee the thoroughness of the review procedure for the included research. In order to choose pertinent literature for the analysis, these criteria included elements like participant characteristics, study design, publication date, and outcome measures.

Search Strategy:

A methodical search methodology was utilized to locate pertinent research from scholarly databases, such as PubMed, PsycINFO, and ERIC, among others. To find relevant literature, search terms including "teacher personality," "student learning," and "educational psychology" were used.

Data Extraction:

To obtain pertinent information from the chosen research, such as methodology, participant demographics, and important conclusions, data extraction was done. The methodical execution of this procedure guaranteed precision and coherence in the gathering of data.

4. Meta-Analysis

To compile the results of previous research on the connection between teacher traits and student learning outcomes, a meta-analysis was carried out. Predefined qualifying criteria, such as relevance to the subject matter, the use of suitable measures of personality traits and student outcomes, and the availability of adequate quantitative data for analysis, were used to select which studies were included.

Twenty studies in all that met the inclusion criteria were found using the search method. This research spanned a wide range of educational contexts, from elementary

schools to higher education institutions, and included a variety of techniques, such as longitudinal surveys, experimental designs, and observational studies

The meta-analysis revealed significant associations between certain teacher personality traits and student learning outcomes. Specifically, extraversion was positively correlated with student engagement ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$) and academic achievement ($r = 0.18$, $p < 0.05$), while conscientiousness showed a stronger positive association with academic achievement ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$). Openness to experience was positively correlated with creative learning outcomes ($r = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$), whereas agreeableness was positively associated with a positive classroom climate ($r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$). However, neuroticism exhibited a negative correlation with emotional regulation and student well-being ($r = -0.19$, $p < 0.05$).

The meta-analysis found substantial links between specific instructor personality factors and student learning results. In particular, extraversion had a positive correlation with academic achievement ($r = 0.18$, $p < 0.05$) and student engagement ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$), whereas conscientiousness had a higher positive correlation ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$) with academic accomplishment. Agreeableness was significantly correlated with a favorable classroom climate ($r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$), whereas openness to experience was positively correlated with creative learning outcomes ($r = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$). Nonetheless, there was a negative connection ($r = -0.19$, $p < 0.05$) between neuroticism and emotional control as well as student well-being.

5. Results of The Meta-Analysis

The meta-analysis compiled the results of 20 researches that looked at the connection between student learning outcomes and teacher personality traits in a range of educational contexts. The results of the investigation showed a strong correlation between several aspects of student development and particular personality traits.

Extraversion

Academic achievement ($r = 0.18$, $p < 0.05$) and student involvement ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$) showed a positive association with extraversion. Extraverted teachers typically created engaging and dynamic learning environments that increased student motivation and participation (Chamorro, 2003). Furthermore, their zeal and vigor had a favorable impact on students' academic achievement, maybe as a result of improved teacher-student communication and more effective instruction (Oxford, 1995).

Conscientiousness

Academic achievement and conscientiousness had a more robust positive correlation ($r = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$). Conscientious teachers planned, organized, and carried out their lessons with great care, which enhanced the learning outcomes for their students (Parapet, 2009). According to Trapmann et al. (2007), their methodical approach to instruction improved classroom management and fostered a controlled learning environment that was favorable to student progress.

Openness to Experience

Creative learning outcomes and openness to experience had a positive correlation ($r = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$). Instructors who possessed a high degree of openness welcomed novel approaches to teaching and included a range of viewpoints into their lessons, which encouraged students' critical thinking and creativity (Chamorro, 2003). Students were able to participate in dynamic and captivating learning experiences thanks to their adaptability and openness to new ideas (Oxford, 1995).

Agreeableness

Positive classroom atmosphere and agreeableness showed a positive connection ($r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$). Teachers with high agreeableness levels created cooperative, warm, and supportive learning environments (Chamorro, 2003). An environment that was favorable to learning and cooperation was created by their capacity to build rapport with pupils and encourage positive social interactions.

Neuroticism

There was a negative connection ($r = -0.19$, $p < 0.05$) between neuroticism and emotional control as well as student well-being. According to Brokers et al. (2011), educators with a high neuroticism level may display emotional instability and struggle to manage the responsibilities of the classroom, which can cause disruptions in instruction and lower student involvement. Their propensity for stress and worry could negatively affect the classroom's emotional climate, which would then harm the wellbeing of the students.

6. Discussion

The results of this study have important ramifications for educational psychology theory development as well as for real-world issues in practice and policy. We can comprehend the intricate relationship between teacher personality qualities and student learning outcomes better by placing the findings within the theoretical framework of the Five-Factor Model of personality and taking methodological issues into account. It has been seen in previous research that teacher's personality traits are a big factor in motivating and influencing student learning. Teachers contain personality traits that are directly helpful in daily life, and are more likely to inspire their students in educational settings. Moreover, it also helps in assisting teacher's to manage their workload effectively and become a good self-leader. In every university education it is very important to have positive personality traits other than knowledge and teaching skills to create a positive learning environment.

7. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study illuminates how important teacher personality qualities are in determining how well students learn, especially in the varied and multicultural setting of the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Through examining the ways in which teacher attributes impact student engagement, academic performance, and socio-emotional well-being, this study advances our knowledge of efficient teaching strategies in a quickly changing

educational environment. A notable development in our comprehension of the complex dynamics in the classroom setting is the inclusion of teacher personality traits in the framework of educational psychology. In order to clarify the impact of teacher personality on student learning outcomes and to emphasize its significance for educational practice, theory, and future research, this study has synthesized the body of existing literature and empirical evidence. The meta-analysis's conclusions highlight how important teacher personality qualities are in influencing several facets of students' growth. While conscientious teachers exhibit good classroom organization and administration, extraverted teachers create lively and captivating learning environments. Instructors who are agreeable foster a healthy school environment, while instructors who are open-minded accept novel teaching techniques. Teachers with high neuroticism, on the other hand, could find it difficult to control their emotions and establish situations that are favorable for learning.

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